

Supplementary Material 4

Informed consent form (participants)

Related to

DARE-STROKE: Gamified Digital Augmented-Reality Exercises for neurorehabilitation of individuals recovering from stroke

Team Holocue(X), Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam

- I have read the information letter. I was also able to ask questions. My questions have been adequately answered. I had enough time to decide whether I wanted to participate.
- I understand that participation is voluntary. I also know that I can withdraw or stop my participation at any time. I do not have to say why I want to stop.
- I know that I can withdraw my consent for the use of my data. This has no adverse consequences for me as a patient.
- I give the researcher permission to inform my GP that I am participating in this study.
- I give the researchers permission to collect and use my data, such as disease symptoms and results of standardized clinical tests. The researchers do this only to answer the research question of this study (i.e. determining the clinical feasibility and effectiveness of Strolll).
- I know that, for the purpose of checking the quality of the research, some people can view all my data. These people are listed in the information letter. I give these people permission to view my data for this purpose.
- I will return the glasses with the Strolll exercise program to the researchers after the training.

- Please indicate ‘yes’ or ‘no’ in the table below.

I give permission to store my data for use in other research, as described in the information letter.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>
I give permission to ask me after this study if I want to participate in a follow-up study.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>
I give permission to use video material made during this study for publication of the results and/or for presentations about this study at conferences or other events. I know that I may be recognizable.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>

- By signing I indicate that I want to participate in this study.

My name is (participant):

Signature:

Date : __ / __ / __

I confirm that I have fully informed this participant about the study described above. If information emerges during the research that could influence the participant's willingness to participate, I will inform this participant in a timely manner.

Researcher's name (or representative):.....

Signature:.....

Date: __ / __ / __

Informed consent form (therapists)

Related to

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Team Holocue(X), Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam

- I have read the information letter. I was also able to ask questions. My questions have been adequately answered. I had enough time to decide whether I wanted to participate.
- I understand that participation is voluntary. I also know that I can withdraw or stop my participation at any time. I do not have to say why I want to stop.
- I give the researchers permission to collect my answers on the questionnaires using a code and to use them for the publication of the results. The researchers do this only to answer the research question of this study (i.e. determining the clinical feasibility and effectiveness of Stroll).
- Please indicate 'yes' or 'no' in the table below.

I confirm that I will be taking part in the DARE-STROKE project and will use Stroll during the treatment of one or more people post-stroke.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>
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- By signing I indicate that I want to participate in this study.

My name is:

Signature:

Date : __ / __ / __

I confirm that I have fully informed this participant about the study described above.

Researcher's name (or representative):.....

Signature:.....

Date: __ / __ / __